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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Back ground: Various studies have reported that loss of one or both parents to AIDS confronts children with immense psychological and social problems and this forces them to employ various coping mechanisms to overcome the problems they encounter in their day to day lives. Consequently, the psychological well-being of these children has become a serious concern.

Objectives: To assess the factors associated with psychological distress of AIDS orphan adolescent's in Mekelle city, Tigray, Ethiopia.

Methods: Institution based cross-sectional study design was used. Two hundred and ninety three subjects were included in this study between 10-19 age groups. Data was collected using a pretested interviewer-administered structured questionnaire and scales including Hamilton-Anxiety Depression and Rosenberg's rating scale were used to measure the orphans' level of depression, anxiety and self-esteem.

Result: Among the study participants, 74 (25.3%) orphan adolescents were depressed in the week before the survey. Moreover, 52 (17.7%) orphan adolescents were anxious. Self esteem and employment opportunity were the main variables associated with depression and anxiety.

Conclusion: Orphan adolescents are having psychological problems and may be particularly vulnerable group that can affect their present and future life. Thus, a more focused and concerted effort is needed to improve their mental health, Care givers of orphan adolescents, in addition to providing material support such as educational materials, medical and food, further studies should be made to compare the psychological health of AIDS, non-AIDS and non-orphan adolescents. Generally, this study contributes to our understanding of how children respond to parental death.

Keywords: HIV/AIDS, orphans, psychological distress, depression, anxiety, stress, self esteem.

BACKGROUND

Orphaned and vulnerable children are one of the most serious socio-economic and developmental challenges affecting developing countries worldwide, Orphan-hood is frequently accompanied with multidimensional problems; Common reactions of children to the death of a parent include: depression, hopelessness, suicidal ideation, loneliness, anger, confusion, helplessness, anxiety and fear of being alone that can further jeopardize children's prospect. There were 15 million officially reported AIDS orphans globally in 2007 (Cluver and Gardner, 2008). The number of orphans from all causes has risen by more than 50% in sub-Saharan Africa, where an estimated 12 million children & youth have lost one or both parents related to AIDS. This makes the region home to 80% of children & youth in developing world who have lost a parent to the disease (Cluver and Fincham, 2009).

A study in Uganda showed that orphans had greater risk of anxiety, depression and anger than non orphans. Furthermore, orphans had significantly higher scores than non-orphans on individual items in the Beck Youth Depression Inventory that are regarded as particularly "sensitive" to the possible presence of a depressive disorder, i.e. vegetative symptoms, feelings of hopelessness, and suicidal ideation (Atwin B. Cantor G. E.2005). Similarly, according to quantitative and qualitative study conducted in Eastern Zimbabwe orphans were found to suffer greater psychological distress than non-orphans (Nyamukapaab C.A. et.al. 2010).

Another study in South Africa showed that children orphaned by AIDS were more likely to report symptoms of depression, peer relationship problems, post-traumatic stress, delinquency and conduct problems than both children orphaned by other causes and non-orphaned children. AIDS-orphaned children were more likely to report suicidal ideation (Cluver L, Gardner F, Operario D. (2007).

An estimated 5, 459, 139 orphans of whom 16% were AIDS orphans existed in Ethiopia in 2008 FHAPCO (2007). The Tigray Region HIV/AIDS Prevention and Control Office reported that there were 94, 848 AIDS orphans in 2008 (Mums, for Mums 2011).

The challenges and needs faced by orphans and other children made vulnerable by HIV/AIDS are diverse. Psychosocial distress (mainly associated with anxiety, loss of parental love and nurture, burden of caring for the sick, impact of family dissolution, depression, stigma, discrimination, grief and frustration (Mums, for Mums 2011).

Like adults, children are grieved by the loss of their parents. However, unlike adults children often do not feel the full impact of the loss simply because they may not immediately understand the finality of death. This prevents them from going through the grieving process which is necessary to recover therefore are at risk of growing up with unresolved negative emotions which are often expressed with anger and depression. Unfortunately, adults do not seem to appreciate that children are also adversely affected by bereavement even though they may not have an adult's understanding of death. Little attention is therefore given to children's emotions. Children are not given the required support and encouragement to express their emotions nor are they guided to deal with them (Cluver et al, 2007).

Emotional support needs to be constantly looked at and improved because children will continue to suffer across the world (Cluver et al, 2007). It is therefore appropriate that attention is given to development of sound measures of the situation and well-being of orphans and children affected by AIDS. There are very few researches undertaken in Africa despite the growing concern about the psychological well-being of orphans, except some agencies effort to address the material needs of AIDS orphans, many of the orphans continue to experience emotional and other psychological problems and little is being done in these areas of support (AAHAPCO, 2007).

Young people themselves, working with adults, can provide a useful resource in addressing many of these needs. In addition, exposure to trauma and daily stress were strongly associated with depression- and anxiety-like symptoms, Greater social support, on the other hand, was negatively associated with psychosocial distress symptoms, and positively associated with some aspects of psychosocial well-being. First, there is a lack of adequate information on the nature and magnitude of the problem. Secondly, there is a cultural belief that children do not have emotional problems and therefore there is a lack of attention from adults. Thirdly, since psychological problems are not always obvious, many adults in charge of orphans are not able to identify them; however, even where the problem may have been identified, there is a lack of knowledge of how to handle it appropriately. In many cases, children are punished for showing their negative emotions, thereby adding to their pain. This is the crux of the matter which needs empirical scrutiny (Smart R. 2008)).

Yet there has been little research done on this area and this makes it difficult to gate baseline data on how to evaluate & improve psychological support programs especially in Tigray region and this study was conducted to assess the magnitude and level of the problem and indicate main intervention areas and make recommendations that will point out areas for further research by future investigators and provide insight into program planners and policy makers to review and change or strengthen existing care and support programs for the orphans in the region as well in the country.

METHODS

Study area and study population

To determine the prevalence and assess the factors associated with psychological distress of AIDS orphan adolescents, an institution based cross-sectional study that employs quantitative method was conducted from May to December, 2012 on 3 purposively selected nongovernmental orphanage institutions in Mekelle city. Mekelle is geographically located at 783 kilometers north of the capital city of Addis Ababa, with the population size of 303, 600 (Mekelle municipality statistical data, 2010). Mekelle is considered a Special Zone, and is one of Ethiopia's principal economic and educational centers, with amazing proliferation of institutions of public and private higher learning. The town is also divided into seven administrative parts Hawelty, Hadnet, Ayder, Semean, Kedamay weyane, Adihaki, and Quiha.

Sample size calculation and data collection procedures

Orphan adolescents age from 10-19 who resides at 3 nongovernmental institutions; 15 from HIV/AIDS African service, 200 from Ethiopian Orthodox Church Mekelle child care center & 85 from Human beings association of brotherhood orphanages. All AIDS orphan adolescents in the 3 selected orphanage institutions aged 10-19 years with single or double parental loss by AIDS were included in the study.

From three institutions, with a total size of 300 orphans and the entire population were taken for the study. Since the total population was needed to be studied there was no need of sampling technique.

Structured interviewer administered questionnaire was used for data collection in the nongovernmental institution in Mekelle City. A structured questionnaire was designed from Hamilton Anxiety and depression measurement scale and Rosenberg. Self-Esteem consisting variables that can meet the objective of the study, and was translated into Tigrigna language. Prior to data collection, permission was obtained from the concerned care giver. The data collection was fulfilled by, two supervisors and 5 graduate nurses data collectors. The overall activity was strictly followed by the principal investigator daily to ensure the completeness of questionnaire, to give further clarification and support for data collectors. The data collectors submitted the filled questionnaire to their respective supervisor, and then all the collected data were checked for completeness, accuracy and consistency by the supervisor and principal investigator.

Quality control measures

To assure the quality of data, the questionnaires were prepared first in English then translated to Tigrigna (local language) by a language expert. Questionnaire was Pre-tested in a community similar to the study population, but out of the selected orphanage institution and care was taken not to include those who already participated in the pre-testing of the questionnaire and amendment was made accordingly. A two days training complemented with practical exercise was given to data collectors and supervisors before the actual data collection regarding the aim of the study.

Data analysis

Data entry and processing was done using SPSS version 16. During the process of analysis, frequencies of different variables were determined. Descriptive statistics was used for describing the socio-demographic factors. Odds ratios with 95% confidence interval were used to assess significance of associations between outcome variables and certain independent variables. Multivariate was done to assess presence of associations as well as to identify and control for confounding variables. The results of the analysis are presented in tables.

Ethical consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from ethical committee of Mekelle University. Respondents participated based on their willingness. The privacy and dignity of every individual involved in the research was protected. Letter of acceptance or permission was obtained from the care givers and respondents of the selected three institutions. In the training session, the data collectors were oriented on the objectives of the study, how to collect data and confidentiality of information were obtained. Finally, the participants was assured confidentiality through identification coding and reports of aggregate data.

RESULT

A total of 293 orphan adolescents gave valid responses making the response rate for the study of 97%. Of these, 154 (52.6%) were male and 139 (47.4%) female adolescents. The mean age was 15.2 with a SD \pm 2.59 years. Majority of the respondents 180 (61.4%) within the age range of 16-19 had depression and anxiety. Almost all 292 (99.6%) of study participants were Orthodox Christians by religion. Regarding orphaned type; One hundred and ninety-two (65.5%) double, sixty seven (22.9%) paternal and thirty-four (11.6%) were maternal orphaned, majority of the orphans 280 (95.6) were enrolled in school when this survey was underway. From the total respondents, 117 (39.9%), 154(52.6%) and 22(7.5%) were elementary, high school and college students respectively (table 1)

The prevalence of depression and anxiety was high in High school students age 16-19 than elementary students age 10-15. Females develop depression and anxiety in 40 (54.1%), 28 (53.8%) while males develop depression and anxiety 34 (45.9%), 24 (46.2%) when this survey was conducted (Table 5)

Of the study participants, 274 (93.5%) have access to health care, 252 (86%) counseling service, 130 (44.4%) psychosocial participation, 97 (33.1%) sociopolitical involvement, and 192 (65.5%), have employment opportunity (Table 6).

Among the orphans who have low self esteem 7 (36.8%) have no access to health care, 7 (17.1%) have no access to counseling services, 18(17.8%) have no employment opportunity and 6 (23.1%) of orphans have community discrimination (Table 7).

Those AIDS orphan adolescents who were not accessed to counseling service and Employment opportunity were (OR=2.78 95% CI: 1.12, 6.98) and (OR= 2.49 95% CI: 1.17, 5.29) more likely to be Anxious as compared to those who have access to counseling services and employment opportunity. Those who have High level of self esteem were [OR 95% CI = .064(.027, .155) less likely to develop anxiety as to compare with those

who have Low level of self esteem. As score of self-esteem Increased and having employment opportunity the probability of being depressed and anxious declines (Table 7, 8).

Those who have no Employment opportunity and not being involved in psychosocial participation and who have discrimination by their community were [OR=2.314 95% CI: 1.18, 4.501), (OR= 2.672 95% CI: 1.233, 5.792) more likely to develop Depression. As compared to those who were not respectively. Orphans who have no discrimination by their community and those who have High level of self esteem were (OR .320 95% CI = .117, .870), [OR=.070 95%CI: (.028, .179) less likely to develop depression than those who are discriminated and having low self esteem (Table 9).

DISCUSSION

The determination of prevalence of psychological distress and associated factors of AIDS orphan adolescents is important because orphan hood by AIDS causes psychological distress particularly vulnerable group in terms of emotional and psychological problems which will certainly affect their present and future life. Assessment helps in planning intervention activities for the prevention of these problems in the orphanages institutions and community. Following the death of parents, children need emotional/psychological support, care and assistance in coping with and/or avoiding stigmatization and socialization.

In this study, 74 (25.3%) of orphan adolescents were depressed and 52 (17.7%) were anxious in the week before the survey. This prevalence is relatively lower than the prevalence of anxiety and depression study done (2010) in Addis Ababa in which 157 (39.1%) depressed and 164(40.8%) were anxious respectively (Hiwot et al, 2011).

This difference could be explained by the fact that, in the current study there was high coverage of counseling service as 252 (86%) have got the service. In addition low level of community discrimination or psychosocial participation, level of self esteem and employment opportunity made them less vulnerable than the previous study. However, the study in Addis Ababa, only (16.2%) AIDS orphan adolescents were provided counseling services showing low coverage (Hiwot et al, 2011). On similar study done in Uganda, only material provision and support without psychosocial support did not show any relationship with the psychological outcomes for the AIDS orphan adolescents (Atwin B Cantor-Graae. 2005).

In this study, it was found out that AIDS orphan adolescents were having psychological problems similar to the study in South Africa and study from Addis Ababa (Culver and Operario, 2008). Similarly, in a study in Uganda, AIDS orphan adolescents were more depressed and anxious as compared to non-orphaned adolescents (Atwin B. Cantor-Graae E. 2005).

In this study, it was also found out that the higher the self esteem the lower was the probability of being anxious and depressed, similar to studies done in Uganda in 2009, South Africa in 2007 and China in 2010 (Cluver and Fincham, (2009); Carol Anzivor, JA. (2007); Hong and Lix, (2010). In this study, it was also found that self esteem and community discrimination is highly likely to result in major emotional problems on AIDS orphan adolescents, similar to study in South Africa 2007 (Cluver and Gardner, 2007).

The majority of the orphans, 280(95.6%) were enrolled in school when this survey was underway; similarly, in a study in Addis Ababa, 368 (91.5%) of AIDS orphans were enrolled in school, the reason for not enrolling in schools included giving priority to money earning activities, feeling of hopelessness and home chores. However, the reason for not enrolling in school in this study was self interest in job employment after accomplishment of grade ten. The common statistically associated variable of depression and anxiety in this study were score of self-esteem which explained the largest percent of variation as compared to other variables of the same study done in Addis Ababa (Hiwot et al, 2011). Likewise studies from Bulawayo, Zimbabwe showed that females reported markedly higher levels of psychosocial distress than males, which is in line to this study (Horizons final report. (2006)).

Strengths of the study

The study is one of the few contributions in the area of investigations assessing the prevalence of psychological distress and associated factors among AIDS orphan adolescent in Tigray as well as in the country. Data were collected from the subjects included in the study.

To ensure the data quality, standardized questionnaire was used, pretests done before the data collection and training was provided to data collectors.

Limitation of the study

The fact that the study was done in Mekelle city, makes it difficult to generalize the findings for the whole Tigray. The nature of the study being cross sectional is not the best type of study to establish presence or absence of a cause effect association or relationship.

This is an institutional study and the selection of the institutions to be included in the study was purposive and was not an arbitrary random selection. This would create selection bias and affect the representativeness of the study subjects

To date there are no baseline data available which illustrate the situation of OVC in Tigray region. Due to the unavailability of baseline data, it has become very difficult to know and to evaluate the progress or the prevalence.

CONCLUSION

Children orphaned by AIDS are particularly vulnerable group in terms of emotional and psychological problems which certainly affect their present and future life. Thus, a more focused and concerted effort is needed to improve their psychological sequel of losing a parent to AIDS.

Generally, this study contributes to our understanding of how children respond to parental death. The implication of the study is that organizations who are concerned with the social needs of AIDS orphans should also focus on their psychological/emotional needs as well by strengthening their counseling services and by raising the awareness of the community about the troubles of orphans so that people take the initiative themselves in their immediate communities to support orphans. This is highly essential because when favorable conditions are created there is a good chance that these children may be able to cope relatively well with the trauma of losing their parents. The findings of this study revealed that AIDS orphans experience major psychological effects due to the death of parents. These effects include anxiety, depression, low self esteem, fear and loneliness as to the cause of parental death, and unresolved grief. Thus, it is recommended to people concerned about and working with families affected by HIV/AIDS, such as social welfare officers, medical and nursing practitioners, health care workers, government agencies, nongovernmental orphanage organizations, particularly to the orphanage institutions from where this data was collected. The battle against the HIV/AIDS will only be won by the involvement of all the community members.

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Authors' contributions

SA designed the study, participated in the data collection, performed analysis and interpretation of data and drafted the paper and prepared the manuscript. AA and HB assisted in the design, approved the proposal with some revisions, participated in data analysis, revised subsequent drafts of the paper and prepared manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests.

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Annex

Table 1: The Socio-demographic Characteristics of AIDS Orphan Adolescents in Mekelle Tigray December 2012

Variable	Frequency (N=293)	Percent (%)
Age in year		
10-15	113	38.6
16-19	180	61.4
Religion		
Orthodox	292	99.6
Muslim	1	.3
Sex		
Male	154	52.6
Female	139	47.4
Educational status		
Elementary	117	39.9
High school	154	52.6
College	22	7.5
Schooling		
Out of school	13	4.4
In school	280	95.6
Orphan type		
Maternal	34	11.6
Paternal	67	22.9
Both	192	65.5

Table 2: Assessment of Anxiety level on AIDS orphan adolescents in Mekelle
Tigray Ethiopia, December 2012 (N293)

Variable	No	Yes
Anxious mood	200 (68.3)	93 (31.7)
Tension	200 (68.2)	93 (31.7)
Fear	202 (68.9)	91 (31)
Insomnia	237 (80.9)	56 (19.1)
Intellectual(poor memory)	245 (83.6)	48 (16.4)
Depressed mood	175 (59.7)	118 (40.3)
Somatic(muscular)	275 (93.8)	18 (6.1)
Somatic(sensory)	264 (90.1)	29 (9.9)
Cardiovascular system	268 (91.5)	25 (8.5)
Respiratory system	270 (92.2)	23 (7.8)
Gastrointestinal symptoms	268 (91.8)	25 (8.5)
Genitourinary systems	276 (94.2)	17 (5.8)
Autonomic symptoms	233 (79.5)	60 (20.4)
Behavior at interview	181 (61.7)	112 (38.2)

Table 3: Assessment of Depression on AIDS orphan adolescents in Mekelle
Tigray Ethiopia, December 2012 (N293)

Variables	No	Yes
Sadness	263 (89.7)	30 (10.2)
Hopelessness	261 (89.1)	32 (10.8)
Past failure	272 (92.9)	21 (7.2)
Dissatisfaction	253 (86.4)	40 (13.6)
Guilty	260 (88.7)	33 (11.3)
Punishment	224 (76.4)	69 (23.5)
Self dislike	264 (90.1)	29 (9.9)
Self blame	206 (70.3)	87 (29.7)
Suicidal thoughts	275 (93.3)	18 (6.2)
Crying	253 (86.3)	40 (13.6)
Irritability	250 (85.3)	43 (14.7)
Loss of interest in other People	271 (92.5)	22 (7.5)
Indecisiveness	239 (81.6)	54 (18.4)
Worthlessness	275 (93.8)	18 (6.2)
Loss of energy	211 (72)	82 (28)
Insomnia	247 (84.3)	46 (15.7)
Fatigue	259 (88.4)	34 (11.6)
Decreased appetite	282 (96.2)	11 (3.7)
Weight loss	282 (96.3)	11 (3.7)
Wariness on health	206 (70.3)	87 (29.7)
Change of interest in Sex	204 (69.6)	89 (30.4)

Table 4: Assessment of self esteem on AIDS orphan adolescents in Mekelle Tigray Ethiopia, December 2012 (N293)

Variables	Disagree	Agree
I am satisfied with my self	53 (18.1)	240 (81.9)
I am inclined to feel that I am failure	77 (26.3)	216 (73.8)
I have a number of good qualities	43 (14.6)	250 (85.3)
I am able to do things as most others	52 (17.8)	241 (82.3)
I feel I do not have much to be proud of	84 (28.7)	209 (71.3)
I take positive attitude towards my self	30 (10.1)	263 (89.8)
I feel that I am a person of worth equal with others	35 (11.9)	258 (88)
I wish I could have more respect for my self	54 (18.4)	239 (81.6)
All in all I am inclined to feel that I feel I am a failure	90 (30.8)	203 (69.3)
At times I think I am not good at all	231 (78.8)	62 (21.2)

Table 5: Distribution of depression and Anxiety based on sex and age of AIDS orphan adolescents, in Mekelle Tigray, Ethiopia, 2012 (N293)

Character	Depressed	Non Depressed	Anxious	Non Anxious
Age				
10-15	21 (28.4%)	92 (42.0)	12 (23.1)	101 (41.9)
16-19	53 (71.6%)	127 (58.0)	40 (76.9)	140 (58.1)
Sex				
Male	34 (45.9%)	120 (54.8)	24 (46.2)	130 (53.9)
Female	40 (54.1%)	99 (45.2)	28 (53.8)	111 (46.1)

Table 6: Distribution of access to health service on AIDS Orphan Adolescents in Mekelle Tigray December 2012 (N 293)

Variable	Frequency (%)
Access to health care	
yes	274 (93.5)
no	19 (6.5)
Counseling service	
yes	252 (86.0)
no	41 (14.0)
Community discrimination	
yes	26 (8.9)
no	267 (91.1)
PSS participation	
yes	130 (44.4)
no	163 (55.6)
Sociopolitical involvement	
yes	97 (33.1)
no	196 (66.9)
Employment opportunities	
yes	192 (65.5)
no	101 (34.5)

Table 7: assessment of self esteem in based on access and services in AIDS orphan adolescents, in Mekelle Tigray December 2012 (N293)

Variable	Frequency of (low self esteem)
Employment opportunities	
Yes	20 (10.4)
No	18 (17.8)
Community discrimination	
Yes	6 (23.1)
No	32 (12.0)
Counseling service	
Yes	31 (12.3)
No	7 (17.1)
Access to health care	
Yes	31 (11.3)
No	7 (36.8)

Table 8: Multivariate analysis of variables for anxiety in AIDS orphan adolescents, in Mekelle Tigray, Ethiopia, 2012 (N293)

variables	Level of anxiety		Crude OR (95% CI)	Adjusted OR (95% CI)
	Anxious	Non-anxious		
Self esteem				
Low	24 (46.2%)	14 (5.8%)	1	1 *
High	28 (53.8%)	227 (94.2%)	.072 (.033,.155)	.064 (.027,.155)
Counseling service				
Yes	37 (14.7)	215 (85.3)	1	1 *
No	15 (36.6)	26 (63.4)	3.352 (1.62,6.92)	2.78 (1.112, 6.98)
Age in year				
10-15	12 (10.6)	101 (89.4)	1	1
16-19	12 (10.6)	140 (77.8)	2.405(1.20, 4.81)	1.84 (0.55, 6.08)
PSS participation				
Yes	14 (10.8)	116 (89.2)	1	1
No	38 (23.3)	125 (76.7)	2.519 (1.29, 4.88)	2.03 (0.86, 4.82)
Sociopolitical involvement				
Yes	8 (8.2)	89 (91.8)	1	1
No	44 (22.4)	152 (77.6)	3.22 (1.45, 7.15)	1.874 (0.67, 5.23)
Employment opportunities				
Yes	22 (11.5)	170 (88.5)	1	1 *
No	30 (29.7)	71 (70.3)	3.27 (1.77, 6.05)	2.49 (1.17, 5.29)
Educational status				
Elementary	12 (10.3)	105 (89.7)	1	1
High school	36 (23.4)	118 (76.6)	2.67 (1.32, 5.39)	1.11 (0.325,.325)
College	4 (18.2)	18 (81.8)	1.94 (.564,6.70)	0.84 (0.15,4.72)

Table 9: Final logistic regression model to predict probability of depression in AIDS orphan adolescents, in Mekelle Tigray, Ethiopia, 2012 (N293)

Variable	Level of depression		Crude OR (95% CI)	Adjusted OR (95% CI)
	Depressed	Non depressed		
Level of self esteem				
Low			1	*
High	28 (73.7%) 46 (18.0%)	10 (26.3%) 209 (82.0%)	.079 (.036,.173)	.070 (.028,.179)
Community discrimination				*
Yes	13 (50%)	13 (50%)	1	1
No	61 (22%)	206 (77.2%)	.296 (.130,.672)	.320 (.117,.870)
PSS participation				
Yes	21 (16.2)	109 (83.8)	1	*
No	53 (32.5)	110 (67.5)	2.501(1.413,4.42)	2.672 (1.23,5.79)
Employment				
Yes	34 (17.7)	158 (82.3)	1	*
No	40 (39.6)	61 (60.4)	3.047(1.768,5.2)	2.314(1.189,4.51)
Age in year				
10-15	21 (28.4)	92 (42.0)	1	1
16-19	53 (71.6)	127 (58.0)	1.83 (1.032, 3.24)	1.48 (0.55, 4.0)
Educational status				
Elementary	20 (27.0)	97 (44.3)	1	1
High school	48 (64.9)	106 (48.4)	2.196(1.22,3.97)	1.303 (.465,3.65)
College	6 (8.1)	16 (7.3)	1.82 (.64, 5.22)	1.49 (.360, 6.19)
Type of orphan				
Maternal	12 (16.2)	22 (10.0)	1	1
Paternal	12 (16.2)	55 (25.1)	.400 (.156,1.02)	.372 (.122,1.14)
Both	50 (67.6)	142 (64.80)	.65 (.29, 1.39)	.489 (.186, 1.29)
Access to health care				
Yes	65 (87.8)	209 (95.4)	1	1
No	9 (12.2)	10 (4.6)	2.89 (1.13, 7.43)	1.61 (.488, 5.29)
Counseling service				
Yes	57 (77.0)	195 (89.0)	1	1
No	17 (23.0)	24 (11.0)	2.43 (1.21, 4.02)	1.36 (.56, 3.29)
Sociopolitical involvement				
Yes	16 (21.6)	81 (37.0)	1	1
No	58 (78.4)	138 (63.0)	2.13 (1.15, 3.95)	1.12 (.48, 2.60)

Table 10: level of AIDS Orphan Adolescents who has low self esteem, depression and anxiety within the Last week before the Survey, in Mekelle Tigray, December 2012 (N293)

Self esteem	Yes 38 (13.0)	No 255 (87)
Depression	Depressed 74 (25.3)	None Depressed 219 (74.7)
Anxiety	Anxious 52 (17.7)	None Anxious 241 (82.3)